

Socio-Economic Profile and Planning of Street Venders in Surat

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ABSTRACT

Street vending is an important activity related to informal sector in urban areas as it provides job opportunity and means of livelihood to the urban poor but Urban Local Bodies consider it as illegal activity so far. The present study comprehensively covers the sociological, economic and space issues taking the case of Surat which is one of the fastest growing city and second largest city of Gujarat. In Surat, vendors can be seen all over the city but concentration is very high in major commercial areas that come under the central, west and east zone. Due to predominance of commercial activities in these areas also attract a very large number of people and have become prime location for informal activities like vending. The overall gender distribution indicates clear predominance of male vendors in Surat. Women are marginalized, among most vendor types. About 73% of the space in the natural markets is being used by vendors against movement space for customers and other activities. Opposite relationship has been found between area of the markets and number of the vendors. As the space reduces in comparison to number of vendors the size of unit reduces and its opposite, when number of vendors is less in comparison to the space available, the size of the unit becomes larger.

Keywords: *Street vendors, Migration, Natural market, Gender, Age group, Caste, Religion, Marital status, Location, Family Size, Distance of workplace, Remittances, Space, Investment, Hawking unit, Unit size, Duration of work*

Introduction:

Street vending is an important activity related to informal sector in urban areas as it provides job

opportunity and means of livelihood to the urban poor but Urban Local Bodies consider it as illegal activity so far. In 2004, first time, Government of India recognizes vendor's role in local economy after so many litigations and Supreme Court verdict in favour of vendors. The Draft National Policy on Urban Street Vendor, 2004 and 2009, Model Street Vendors (Protection of Livelihood and Regulation of Street Vending) Bill, 2009 are some of the initiatives taken by the Government to protect the interest of this marginalized group. Organizations have also played major role to push vendors issue and formulation of policies in favour of street vendors.

The present study has comprehensively covered the sociological, economic and space issues taking the case of Surat which is one of the fastest growing city and second largest city of Gujarat, India. The basic aim of the present study is look into socio-economic condition of the street vendors for developing a strategy for its inclusion into formal planning process in Surat City. The study has analyzed the existing concentration of informal shopping and street vendors and also identified issues and required provision of vending facilities for developing the strategy for street vending. A comprehensive survey was undertaken in 23 locations which come under jurisdiction of the Surat Municipal Corporation (SMC).

With increasing urban migration and the shrinking formal sector, hawking and street vending have emerged as one of the critical means of earning a livelihood for the urban poor in India. A street vendor is broadly defined as a person who offers goods or services for sale to the public without having a permanent built up structure but with a temporary static structure or mobile stall (or head load). Street

vendors may be stationary by occupying space on the pavements or other public/private areas, or may be mobile in the sense that they move from place to place carrying their wares on push carts or in cycles or baskets on their heads, or may sell their wares in moving bus etc.

Demography:

Surat growing very fast and according to latest population Census data of 2011 the decadal growth rate is about 42.19, highest in the state of Gujarat. The rate of literacy is quite high and it is 86.65 which are equal to literacy of Ahmedabad which is the largest city of the Gujarat. The population share of the Surat district is also very high and it is about 10.07% of the state. However, city is having lowest sex ratio of 788 females per 1000 of males due to large number of migrants while it is 918 for the state of Gujarat. The sex ratio of 0-6 age group is 836 which also lowest in the state as it is 886 in 2011. The city can be broadly classified into four parts i.e. the old city, the inner periphery around the core city, Rander zone (north of the Tapi River) and the outer periphery (comprising of the newly developed areas). In Surat, there are two main Governing bodies namely, Surat Municipal Corporation (SMC), Surat Urban Development Authority (SUDA). On 8th February, 2007, Union Urban Development Ministry has included Surat city in the group of nine mega cities having global character and high growth potential. The city is largely recognized for its textile and diamond businesses. It is also known as the diamond capital of the world and the textile capital of India. About 92% of the world's diamonds are cut and polished in Surat. It has one of the highest GDP growth rates in India.

It is well known that the economic activities of Surat has not only attracted a substantial amount of capital, but also a proportion of /migrant population from within Gujarat, the neighbouring state Maharashtra as well as farther regions of Uttar Pradesh, Orissa, Andhra Pradesh and Tamilnadu. Migrants from various districts of Maharashtra have been coming to Surat about last six to seven decades. However, the flow of migration from the districts of Uttar Pradesh and Orissa to the city has seemingly been more recent and only since the mid-eighties that the intensity of this flow has increased. Most of these eastern districts of U.P. and the specific regions in Ganjam and Puri in or have about a seventy year old history of outmigration (Das, 1994). The city is largely recognized for its textile and diamond businesses and

92% of the world's diamonds are cut and polished in Surat. Gujarati diamond cutters emigrating from East Africa established the industry in 1901 and by the 1970s Surat-based diamond cutters began exporting stones to the US for the first time. Though much of the polishing work takes place on small weight stones, Surat's workshops have set their eyes on the lucrative market for finishing larger, pricier stones in the future. The November 18, 2008 issue of the Wall Street Journal had an article about the diamond industry in Surat. It claims that 80% of the world's finished diamonds are cut and polished in this city. Surat is also a major production centre for synthetic textiles in India.

Natural Markets:

Few years back SMC has conducted a detailed survey of the vendors in South zone which is having an area of about 61sq.km and reported to have about 2156 vendors. The survey results show that the city is having very large number of Vegetable vendors followed by vendors selling fruits and cooked food. A simple calculation of total area and number of vendors indicates that there are about 35 vendors per sq.km. Looking at the present area under the SMC which is 326 sq.km it is expected to have about 11522 vendors in the city. However, the concentration of vendors found to be very high in central, West zone and East zone the actual number of vendors will be much more than 35 per sq.km. Our personal observation suggest that these three zone will have about 100 vendors per sq.km and it will be about 97009 total area is about 97 sq.km). For the remaining part of the city taking 35 as average number then it is expected to have about 8017 vendors and hence a total of 17717 vendors can be found in the city of Surat which is much lower than the expected number suggested in the National Policy of Street Vendors. The National Policy document stated that there is one to two percent of city population engaged in vending in large cities.

In Surat, vendors can be seen all over the city but concentration is very high in major commercial areas that come under the central, west and east zone. Due to predominance of commercial activities in these areas also attract a very large number of people and have become prime location for informal activities like vending. Transport nodes are the other important location where one can see a large number of vendors are engaged in hawking are also located in these zones. Residential areas are mainly having vendors selling regular commodities like vegetables, fruits and

other items. In addition to the natural markets Surat is also having special weekly markets like Saniwari and Raviwari where one can see a very large number of vendors are engaged in selling different types of goods. The SMC has also taken initiative to settle the vendors in few locations like Bhatar, City Light, Pandeshra housing and Sonal Market. Few items like vegetable and fruits can be seen in almost all the locations. While some markets are specialized in garment or non-vegetarian food items others remained general.

General background of Vendors:

The overall gender distribution indicates clear predominance of male vendors in Surat. Women are marginalized, among most vendor types. Among all the vendors in Surat, females constitute a very small portion, compared to the male street vendors. Of the total number of vendors surveyed, 86.5 % are males and 13.5 % are females. This is nearly equal to the national average of 86 % males, and 14 % females. Generally it has been found that number of males is higher than the females in each economic sector, except very few like home based works. Following to this, the number of female street vendors found in Surat city is only 13.5% against 86.5% male. The markets where only few female street vendors are selling goods are Chauta bazaar, Chauta Bridge, Bhagal, KhaudraGali, Saiyadpura market, Begumpura market, and Chikuwadi (Sonal) market. The problems of women vendors in general, deserve special emphasis and focus in view of their marginal position in the class of vendors. The gender division of vendors is expected to have implications for earnings, regularity of income, and possibility for upward mobility in the vending activity. According to some researchers there are greater disadvantages for women vendors in general, due to various reasons like women don't have sufficient time to buy goods from whole sale market in the morning and sell it throughout the day besides looking home. The gender identities tend to be involved in different activities or types of employment even within the same trade.

Age of the Vendors:

Different age groups often define the kind of vendors and the products which they sell. Our survey shows that nearly half of the vendors are in the age group of 33 – 59 years. Almost 30% are in the age group of 25- 34 years, 14% of the vendors are young, in the age group of 18 - 24 years. Only 1.2% of the vendors

are below 18 years of age. This trend is seen among the vendors selling fruits and vegetables. The vendors across Surat City shows that age- group of below 18 years consists 25% female and 75% male vendors whereas 18- 24 years age- group have 93.5% male and only 6.5 % female vendors. This figure indicates that most of the male vendors joining street vending in young age of 18- 24 years while most of the females, especially in this age- group, don't join vending occupation due to responsibility of care of small children and other family members along with other house work.

Religion and caste:

In case of Surat City there are 77% vendors belongs to Hindu religion while rest of them belongs to Muslim religion. . Greater percentage of Muslim vendors is found selling plastic items, non-vegetarian items, and wooden items. It appears that the traditional skills are linked to religious background of these vendors and food habits are also linked to selling non-vegetarian items. However, it is important to note that fish vendors are mostly women and belongs to lower caste communities. So, there is a complicated relation between cast and vending type. Local factors also affect the selection of vending along with the religion and caste. Majority of general (others) cast people involved in selling fruit juice, food items, leather goods/ footwear, vegetable that require medium and high capital investment to start the business than others. Most of the OBC vendors engaged in selling wooden items and non-vegetarian food. Considerable number of SC vendors selling fruits, cutlery, cosmetics and other items.

Marital status:

Most of (79.7%) the vendors are married while 17.5% unmarried, 1.8% widow and 0.9% divorced or living separate from spouse. Most of the vendors are married. This is mainly because 84.6% vendors are more than 24 years old. Bhagal, Baroda Pristage, VarachaChauptati and PalanpurPatia are the markets where some widow vendors were found during survey while some divorced/ separately living vendors were found in Bhagal, Udhana Station and PalanpurPatia market.

Literacy:

Literacy trends among the street vendors, show that the more illiterate vendors have smaller businesses like fruit stalls. More than 90% of all surveyed

vendors are literate, and have studied at least up to 5th grade. Literacy trends among the street vendors show that the more illiterate vendors have smaller businesses like small fruit stalls. Literacy is high among the vendors selling vegetables, food items, cloth, footwear and miscellaneous items.

Migration:

There is 40.6% vendors migrated from outside the Gujarat where as 21.8% migrated to Surat within Gujarat. Hari Nagar-2, APMC, Chikuwadi, Pandeshra, City Light are few markets consist more than 60% of street vendors from outside the Gujarat. Most of the migrated street vendors belong to Uttar Pradesh, Bihar and Maharashtra. Migrated vendors are mainly engaged in selling vegetable, fruit, stationary/ bag and cosmetic products.

Most of the vendors (96.6%) migrated from rural areas. Only 0.92% came from large cities in search of better job opportunities. This figure shows the highly deprived rural India; with respect to job opportunity simultaneously it shows the potential of cities to provide job to unskilled, low educated people as street vendor.

Duration of the stay in the market:

Data regarding migrated vendors living in the Surat shows that maximum (35.8%) vendors living here more than 15 years and 23.0% from more than last 10 years. In Surat some location like Hari Nagar- 2, Trikumpura and Ring Road are some market where more than 60% vendors selling goods for more than 15 years. In fact many of the vendors have started their business in this market, or have been second or third generation vendors in this market. Most of the vegetable, fruit juices, cloth, footwear, bags, cosmetics and wooden item vendors, have come to the markets more than 15 years ago.

Family Size:

The size of the family affects of quality of life of human beings. The quality of life does not only pertain to economic standards of living, rather it has a much wider horizon. Family size affects: basic human needs, income and growth of the economy and savings, food and nutrition-quality and quantity, uses of land and urban public system, health, especially that of mother and child, and education, particularly that of children. In case of street vendors of Surat, most of (79.7%) vendors have 2-4 members in their

family while 14.2% have 5- 8, 4.0% have 9- 11 and only 2.2% have >11 member in the family. Shaniwari, Bhagal, Begumpura and Santosh Nagar (Ravivari) are the markets where some vendors have more than eight members in the family.

Figures related to number of family members staying in Surat reveals that majority of vendors living without family in the Surat. They are living alone or with the one family member who is also working. Migrated vendors come alone and send the profit to their family. The vendors who are living with 1-2 and 3- 4 family members become 38.5% & 46.5%. Only 4.3% vendors living with more than six family members that indicates they are living with their family in Surat.

Number of family members working:

Majority of (63%) vendors working alone in their house while 21% vendors have two working person in their house. Only 6% vendors having more than four persons working in their house. There is high concentration of street vendors, who migrated alone from their native place to get means of livelihood. Chauta bazaar, Chauta bridge, Saiyadpura, APMC, City Light and Mora Bhagal are some of the markets which consists more than 80% street vendors who working alone in their family.

Commercial and economic information:

Mode of travel to the working place: The mode of travel is especially important for vendors who are buying regularly from the wholesale market and then selling it as vendor. In Surat about one third vendors are travelling by private vehicle to the market. One third vendors are also going by foot and almost one fifth of them are using public transport. So, public transport as a mode of travel for vendors is not very popular in Surat.

Distance of workplace:

Data regarding distance of workplace to home shows that vendor prefers living near to work place that's why 63% vendors living within 2 km distance from the market. In the established market where permanent structure has been provided by SMC, the vendors like to leave close to the market because they know this place is permanent and they are not going to evict from this place in future. Chikuwadi (Sonal) market is established by SMC, where 60% vendors living less than 0.5 km distance from the market.

MoraBhagal is the market where 67% vendors come from more than 5 km distance to sell the goods. It's because Mora Bhagal is located the outside of old city and most of the vendors come from outskirts with grown commodities in their farm.

Reasons for entry in to this occupation:

In Surat, a large number of vendors 29% are engaged in this occupation because it's their family occupation. Mora Bhagal, Saiyadpura and Bhagal are some of the old markets where most of the vendors' responded that they are carrying this business due to the fact that it is inherited. The share of vendors who are involved in street vending due to less investment, need of money and past experience in this kind of business, are 11%, 15% and 10% respectively.

Vending type shows that 39% vegetable and 67% non-vegetarian food vendors come in this occupation because of family business. Major portion of vegetable vendors, fruit vendors, food item vendors, non-vegetarian vendors, cutlery, and cosmetic vendors quoted family business as the primary reason for being in this occupation.

More than half of the vendors (55.7%) have selected the place of vending due to reasons like closeness to an established market or good opportunity for selling of their goods. It is important to note that vendor's do not bothered about SMC's support in providing them space, or any other amenities. Less than one percent of the vendors reported that they selected this area because SMC has provided the structure and space for vending.

The market-wise information shows that in some markets like Hari Nagar- 2, Kailash Nagar and BhatarTenament, most of the vendors preferred this location because of nearness to their house. On the other hand Chauta bazaar, Saiyadpura and Mora Bhagal are the markets where vendors like to sell goods because of well-established market. In general, more than 30% vendor selected the area/ market to run their business as it was already an established market area.

Remittances to home:

Around 62% vendors are migrated and 32% of them are sending remittances to home and 30% vendors don't send. It denotes half of the migrated vendors are not sending money to their families due to various reasons.

Type of markets where vendors buy goods:

Majority (54%) of the vendors buy goods from whole sale market while 26% vendors from super markets. APMC is the main whole sale market of vegetable and fruit while Bombay market is known for cloths where most of the vendors buy goods in Surat.

Ownership of Space:

Except few locations almost all the vendors are using public space for selling goods. Only 3.4% vendors are using private land. The markets which are mostly using private land are Pandeshra Housing, Hari Nagar- 2 and KhaudaraGali.

Investment made to setup the stall:

Study regarding investment made to set up the stall by vendors shows that 28.0% vendors invested Rs. 3000-6000 and same number of vendors invested Rs. 6000-12000.

In some locations like Hari Nagar- 2, Kailash Nagar, City Light, Mora Bhagal, Piplod 50% to 65% vendors replied that they invested Rs. 3000- 6000 for setting stall. Saiyadpura, Sonal and City Light are the markets where 50 to 75% vendors invested Rs. 6000-12000 for setting a stall. It is important to note that both Sonal Market as well as City light has been developed by the SMC.

Turnover (monthly): In response of turnover, about 28.3% vendors have informed that their monthly turnover is Rs. 5000- 15000 and 24.6% vendors' turnover is Rs. 15000- 30000. There are some (7.4%) vendors have monthly turnover more than Rs. 90,000. Begumpura, Kailash Nagar, City Light and Piplod are markets where turnover is Rs. 5000- 15000 for more than 50.0% of total vendors. Chauta Bridge, Trikumpura, Pandeshra housing are the markets where turnover is in the range of Rs. 15000- 30000 for 50.0% vendors. Chauta bazaars, KhaudaraGali, Chikuwadi are the markets where more than 50.0% vendor's monthly turnover is Rs. 30,000 to 60,000/-. Saiyadpura is the market where turnover of 75.0% vendors is more than Rs. 90,000.

The vendors, who have turnover less than Rs 5000, are mainly 15 % cloth vendors, 28.5 % plastic item vendors, 50 % wooden item vendors, and 18 % cosmetic vendors. Nearly one fourth of the vendors selling non-vegetarian items have a monthly turnover of above Rs 90,000.

Income (per day): More than one third (35.4%) vendors per day profit is Rs. 100- 250 whereas 32.6% vendors per day profit is Rs. 250- 500. Location wise information shows that Chauta bazaar, Chauta bridge, Begumpura, Trikumpura, Udhana Station and Chikuwadi are the markets where 50.0% to 80.0% vendors per day profit is Rs. 100- 250 or average income is Rs.175 per vendors. Income of Surat vendors found more as compared to vendors in other cities like Ahmedabad. The average income for each of the vendors in Surat is Rs.235 which is slightly on the higher side if we compare it with income information from other cities. Among all the selected location vendors in Saiyedpura market are earning more than any other location while it is lowest in Bhatar.

Payment of rent:

Data related to type of unit shows that 82.8% vendors aren't paying rent for the space they are using for vending. Only 17.2% vendors are paying rent for the space used by them. So, there is lot of potential if street vendors are regularized in Surat by paying the rent for the space they use. If 82.8% vendors will be paying charges to SMC for used space it might become a large amount which will enable the Corporation to provide the necessary services like toilet, arrangements for solid waste management and other required services. During the survey most of the vendors also expressed their willingness to pay charges if they get recognition and facilities from SMC.

Paying fine:

According to data collected by vendors, 45.2% vendors have paid fine in the past. Some vendors were actually afraid of giving the information due to sensitivity of this issue. Vendors who are on the outer part of the street are more vulnerable as they become the first target of eviction when the SMC or police come for it. Many a time vendors get some information before eviction takes place, so that they can leave the place along with their goods before the arrival of officials or the police.

Source of Investment:

According to Bhowmik (2000), the source of working capital for hawkers is mainly moneylenders as very few of the hawkers get credit from formal sources like credit societies. Other source of funding is from friends and relatives. It is the delay in availability of

credit from banks and Govt. Institutions that discourages hawkers and force them to turn to private money lenders who charge high interest rates. The other popular source of credit availability are the family members or close relatives which seem to be a safer option as they don't charge interest and the repayment options also quite flexible in their case.

The condition of Surat vendors, in terms of source of investment, isn't exceptional than the other cities. During the study it has been found that most of the vendors either taken loan from the money lenders on high interest rate or supported by their family/ relatives/ friends. Some vendors have been taking goods from wholesalers or agents on credit and paying back after selling the goods.

Hawking unit:

Majority of hawking units 54% are mobile in nature while 39% units are stationary in Surat. Other 7% units are neither mobile nor stationary; it means these vendors selling their goods by both ways, sometimes of the day they sell as mobile vendor and sometimes as stationary. APMC, Trikumpura, Kailash Nagar, Pandeshra housing, Bhatar, PalanpurPatia are the markets where more than 70% vending units are mobile. Chautabridge is the market where all vending shops are mobile. Here all vendors selling goods mainly cloths along one side of the road, in front of formal shops. KhaudraGali, Jhapabazaar ,Hari Nagar-2, Baroda Pristage, Ring Road and Piplod are the markets where more than 60.0% hawking units found stationary in nature.

Majority of the fruit sellers and bag sellers are mobile vendors. Other types of vendors, where a large portion is mobile are vegetables, food items, juice, cloth, cosmetics. Only 27.7% of the non vegetarian item sellers are mobile. This may be attributed to the type of products sold.

Mode of operation:

Majority of vendors selling their goods on sitting ground with sheet, handcart becomes second option and kiosk or stall third. Shaniwari, Saiyadpura and Raviwari, Pandeshra housing market and Mora Bhagal are some markets where more than 50.0% vendors selling goods on sitting ground. VarachaChowpati, Kailash Nagar are the markets where more than 60% vendors using handcart for selling goods.

Unit size:

The size of unit is unequal for different type of vendor. But it's not necessary that same type of good selling vendors require same size of space. It depends on the capacity of investment made by the vendor and type of the good selling by the vendor. There management/ arrangement of goods also matters. In case of Mora Bhagal, Shaniwari and Pandeshara Housing market, vendors spade their goods in comparatively large area than the other markets because space is not an issue in these markets. Chauta Bazar that is a congested, old market where space is a major concern, therefore vendors arranged their goods in the manner so that they could accommodate more goods in a small space.

Unit size of 10.8% vendors is less than 10 sq. ft. while 25%, 24%, 22% and 18% vendors unit size is 10- 20 sq. feet, 20- 40 sq. feet 40- 80 sq. feet and more than 80 sq. ft. respectively. Almost 50.0% vendors occupied 10 to 40 sq. ft. space for their vending. Sonal market, City Light and Mora Bhagal are some markets where more than 50% vendors occupying 20-40 sq. feet area. Shaniwari, Jhapa bazaar, UdhanaStation, PalanpurPatia and Ring Road are the markets where more than 30.0% vendors using 40- 80 sq. feet area to make their stall.

Vending type wise data shows that one fourth of vegetable vendors occupy 20- 40 sq. feet area and 23.9% vegetable vendors occupy 40- 80 sq. feet area. Fruit vendors that occupy <10 sq. feet, 10- 20 sq. feet and 20- 40 sq. feet space are 29.2%, 25.0% and 42.9%. One third of the cutlery vendors occupied 10-20 sq. feet space while 37.5% cosmetic product vendors occupied 20- 40 sq. feet area.

Duration of work:

In Surat, majority of the vendors (64%) working whole day followed by 12% vendors who works only at evening and 7% vendors that works only in the morning. Actually working hour depends on the type of commodity. For instance, mostly people wants to buy vegetable at evening while some of them also buy in the morning but nobody usually going to buy vegetable at mid of the day. In the same way mostly ladies want to buy cosmetic products and cloths at mid of the day. This situation is similar to Patna and other cities of India where most of the vendors engaged whole day in vending. In Surat, Shaniwari, Chauta bazaar, Bhagal, APMC, Baroda Pristage,

Santosh Nagar (Raviwari), Udhana Station, PalanpurPatia, Ring Road are some of the markets where vendors selling goods whole day. KahaudraGali, VarachaChaupati and Mora Bhagal are the markets where most of the vendors selling goods at evening.

Locational characteristics and problems:

More than 40.0% vendors believethat established market as important factor whereas 20.3% vendors believe both, high residential density and established market place and 15.4% vendors believe that only high residential density as a major factor for creation of demand. More than 65% vendors of Jhapa bazaar, Chauta bazaar, APMC, Trikumpura and Mora bhagal markets, have considered established market as the important factor while more than 50% vendors of Hari Nagar- 2, Kailash Nagar, Pandesara Housing, Bhatar Market and Piplod considered high residential density as important factor. Most of the vendors (80.0%) of Ring Road market reported, high traffic density is the important factor for creation of demand for their goods.

In response to the factors that influence the selling of commodity, large number (55%) of vendors reported festival and 31% vendors reported weather as important factor whereas 14% vendor have reported other reasons. Chautabridge, Begumpura, Pandeshra housing, Mora bhagal, Ring Road and Piplod are the markets where more than 80% vendors considered festival as the important factor for influencing the sale of goods.

Vending type wise data shows that 52% vegetable, 54% fruit, 54% food items, 52% cloth, 71% plastic items, 73% foot wear/ leather goods, 100% cutlery and 50% cosmetic product vendor reported festivals as influencing factor for selling of goods where as large number (89%) of fruit juice vendor reported weather as influencing factor. Items like fruit juices are in high demand during the summer months. Those who are selling spices reported that during the summer months people buy spices for storing as well as making pickles. The demand of cloths, footwear, cosmetics and cutlery also influenced by marriage seasons as well as festival.

Membership of an organization: There are only 3.1% of vendors are member of any vendor organization. There are only a few vendor organizations identified in the 23 studied markets. These are, VyapparMandal

in Baroda Pristage (established in 2002), Den DayalMandal in Chikuwadi (Sonal) market and Sai Association in Pandeshra Housing market. Majority of vendors are member of aforesaid associations in these markets. But rest of the markets doesn't have any association except Kailash Nagar market. This shows that there is no organization at city level in Surat that can raise genuine issues concerned to large number of the vendors.

There are only few vendors found aware about National Policy on Urban Street vendors in the markets where vending organization exists. So we can say associations play vital role to aware vendors about their rights and limitations.

Future aspirations in this area:

It's important to know what vendors think about promotion/ upgradation of their livelihood. During the survey most of the vendors (37.8%) want to buy a shop, 35.1% want to rent a shop, 10.2% vendors want to get rented hand carts (larries) , 9.5% want to send more remittances to their home and 4.3% want to get their family in Surat. Only 1.2% vendors aspire various other things. Raviwari, Shaniwari, Saiyadpura, Begumpura and Mora-bhagal are the markets where more than 80.0% vendors wish to buy shop in the existing market. Chauta bazaar, Pandesara Housing and Ring Road are the markets where 68.8%, 72.7% and 80.0% of the total vendors want to rent a shop in the market.

Aspirations for future generation: Majority of the vendors (85%) don't want their son/ daughters to continue this trade. Most of them informed that they are doing very hard work throughout the day but they don't earn as per their requirement while some of them informed that they are facing eviction and extortion problems and don't want their son/ daughter will face these problems.

Vendors are facing several problems as there are 51.4% vendors who reported they are facing problems of some kind, while the rest remain tight mouthed about any kind of problems being faced by them. Out of 51.4% of vendors 22.4% have faced problem of harassment by authorities, 16.9% have faced problem of eviction, 2.8% have faced conflict with pedestrians, and 0.9% have faced confiscation of goods and 0.9% extortion by authority. In some location like Hari Nagar-2, Udhana Station and Kailash Nagar are the markets where 85.7%, 50.0% and 50.0% vendors

facing the problem of harassment by authorities. Chauta bazaar, Trikumpura, Pandesara Housing and PalanpurPatia are the markets where more than 60% vendors facing problem of eviction drives.

Vendor's expectations from local authority reflect their perspective towards what support they are seeking to upgrade their means of livelihood. Most of the vendors (62.2%) reported that they have some expectation from local authority while 37.8% vendors don't have any expectation. Out of 62.2% of total vendors, 28.6% expect space with license ID, 15.7% expect only space, 8.3% expect space with basic facilities like water and sanitation, 4.9% expect only license ID and 4.6% expect only basic facilities from the SMC. Many vendors have expressed their requirement of additional space so that they can bring more goods and earn little more. For the extension of vending activity there is a need of additional space this will also help them to improve their means of livelihood. However, in Surat majority of vendors (72.3%) don't require additional space against 27.7% vendors who require additional space. So, most of the vendors are able to manage their business in the available space and getting extra space for vending is not the immediate requirement.

In many locations vendors are ready to pay for additional space and this denotes the actual number of vendors who require addition space, because if a vendor would really require additional space, he must be agreed to pay for this. Survey results shows that majority of vendors (80.0%) are agree to pay for additional space. It means most of the vendors who reported requirement of additional space are actually needed for this. Shaniwari, Chautabridge, KhaudaraGali, Hari Nagar- 2, Trikumpura, Raviwari, Pandeshra, Mora Bhagal, Ring Road, Piplod are the markets where most of the vendors replied that they are agree to pay for additional required space. There is also higher percentage of hawkers found in Ahmedabad, who are willing to pay for additional space.

In Surat, a large number of vendors (78.8%) don't agree to relocate from original place while 21.2% agreed on condition that their requirements are taken care in new location. PalanpurPatia, Kailash Nagar and Sonal Market are the markets where more than 50% of the vendors are ready to relocate from the present place. In case of PalanpurPatia most of the vendors are already relocated to formal structures. But most of them are still vending along the road which is

part of a four lane road passing through this area. As they are sitting on the road these vendors are more vulnerable to eviction.

Natural market designs and occupied space:

Natural markets are the result of natural process and are not developed by any administrator/ authority. It is also seen that some of the markets are very old while few are relative new or of moderate age (20-25 years) and some of them are newly developed in the last few years. The physical shapes of these markets are not uniform as it is adjusted along with nearby road, open space and traffic movement. However, these shapes are linked to possibility of developing a general framework for physical design of these markets or possibility of future growth.

Urban Planners should take care of natural heredity of informal markets while making plan for urban renewal, road widening or relocation of natural market. If the new roads has been designed for an urban area or the project of urban renewal/ road widening will be prepared, planners must accommodate the vendors as a part of the scheme. So it will be good if street vendors will be accommodated in the plane before happening this natural process along the road in commercial and residential area of the city.

Each natural market has its own charm. The naturally grown markets along the road are main characteristic of all Indian cities. These markets should be conserved as heritage rather than removal. Despite the removal or shifting of natural markets to the formal markets there should be focus on accommodating these vendors in the urban areas following the natural designs of markets because development of street vending is much related to the natural process rather than planned activity. If any area will be developed and demand will be created, street vending will grow automatically.

Empirical evidence suggests that urban planning that attempts to ignore natural markets ultimately fails to protect either the right of street vendors to do their business or the right of commuters to move freely through public space. This is because the failure to accommodate natural markets in the regulatory framework does not effectively prevent these markets from forming and the situation becomes one where

the vendors remain illegal and the consumers are inconvenienced.

Forcing street vendors out of natural markets, by contrast, would block efficient economic transactions and leads to economic waste. Allowing for natural markets not only maximizes the productivity of street vendors themselves, but also of their consumers. The individual consumer benefits greatly from the presence of street vendors in natural markets. But in addition, the convenience that natural markets provide to individual consumers translates, in the aggregate, to greater overall efficiency from the macroeconomic standpoint.

The average size of vending unit is 2.3 sq.mt. for all natural markets. Space occupied by each vendor in City light and Sonal vegetable market hasn't been calculated because these are formal markets and most of the vendors using space as per assigned to him by SMC. Hari- Nagar- 2 market has maximum vending unit size whereas Jhapa bazaar has minimum. The cloth markets of Shaniwari and Raviwari have almost same size of hawking unit i.e. 2.4 and 2.5 sq.mt. Hari-Nagar-2 has maximum unit size because there is huge place available as compare to number of vendors. Here, street vendors are not making stall in compact manner. The space between two units has found much than other markets. Jhapa bazaar have minimum size of units because majority of vendors selling commodities in basket or on the small platform except mutton/ chicken vendors. Vegetable, fruit, newspaper and egg vendors mainly occupy small space in this market.

Space of movement Vs Space occupied by vending units:

The total area of market comprises of two spaces i.e. space occupied by vendors and movement space. Chauta bazaar is the market where almost half of the space is used by vendors as making stall against half of the movement space. Piplod is another market where almost 66% market area is used by vendors. Chautabridge is the place where least space is used by customers (only 15%) because small vendors selling on foot way in front of formal shops. Other markets where movement space is less than 20% of the market area are Jhapa bazaar, Trikam Nagar and Bhatar market.

Broadly it can be derived that only 73% of the space in the natural markets is being used by vendors

against movement space for customers and other activities. Opposite relationship has been found between area of the markets and number of the vendors. As the space reduces in comparison to number of vendors the size of unit reduces and its opposite, when number of vendors is less in comparison to the space available, the size of the unit becomes larger.

The detailed analysis of the total area and area occupied by the vendors' shows that most of the locations are not having space for new vendors. The problem of the existing vendors can be sorted out in a planned manner without reducing the space used for movement and in few cases it will ultimately reduce the area of the market. The Second inference that derived from table 8.2 is that in case of vendors of a particular location needs to be shifted to other place the ratio of space for movement and making stalls should not be less than 30% against space proposed for making stalls otherwise it will create congestion. This requirement is not taken the parking requirements for the buyers.

There is an urgent need to address the problems of the street vendors in Surat and SMC has to find appropriate strategy for inclusion of street vendors in the city. The National Policy stresses on demarcation of "Hawking" and "No- Hawking Zones". The policy says that "designation of vendors market/ no vending zones should not be left to the sole discretion of any civic or police authority but must be accomplished by the participatory process". As there are hawking and no- hawking zones are demarcated in Surat City, there is need to accommodate the street vendors that make stalls in the markets come under no- hawking zone like Trikam Nagar. Relocation or accommodation of vendors in these markets can be done through participatory process as suggested in the National Policy. Before bringing any street under no-hawking zone it is essential to have specific rehabilitation strategy for the vendors going to be affected. For this purpose a city level advisory body can be formed. Such body should have adequate representation of the vendors and other civil society groups as suggested in the National policy. It will help to reduce the possible conflict between vendors and SMC/ City Police.

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